

Solarpunk as a maker imaginary

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Abstract

The characteristics of ‘solarpunk’ as an eco-feminist future vision resonates with maker cultures that espouse autonomous development of products and technologies that use renewable energy sources, foster community resilience, accord with principles of environmental justice, and highlight symbiosis with nature and natural systems, even in urban contexts. In this study, we examined solarpunk in online discourse, project descriptions, Fab Academy project concepts, and academic publications, to see how it has travelled from its origins as a sci-fi literary genre to other creative fields, especially design, engineering and fab lab contexts. While there is no agreement on what constitutes solarpunk and what not, we see potential for the concept as a sociotechnical imaginary to motivate fablabbers into more environmentally oriented work in the face of environmental and social crises. Solarpunk may provide impetus in maker culture for alternative organizing and community governance models, to strengthen resistance to capitalist encroachment, precarity and collapse, in a way that is still pragmatic, anti-dystopian and materialist. The study also provides STS insights into how sociotechnical imaginaries may be shaped from below.

Keywords

Solarpunk, sociotechnical imaginaries, environmental sustainability, maker culture, futures

1 Introduction

‘Solarpunk’ is a subgenre of science fiction often described as eco-futurist. It is also a term, narrative, vision, aesthetic – or all of the above – that has transcended its literary traditions, reaching wider creative arenas such as film, art and architecture. Proponents of solarpunk espouse its characteristics as represented in material solutions, buildings, infrastructures and urbanscapes: autonomously developed and independent of mainstream corporate capitalism; community oriented; DIY, creative and ingenious in re-use; and nature- and ecology-oriented, not least in terms of renewable energy sources (Flynn, 2014; Hamilton, 2019; Hunting, 2020). This is ripe territory for fablabbers and characteristics that resonate with the ethos of maker cultures that aspire to socially good, local production as justice-oriented alternatives to consumerism.

Indeed, for researchers of and writers about open source counter-culture design such as Eric Hunting (2021), solarpunk envisions a “maker-hero” as counterpoint to the hacker-hero of cyberpunk: an archetype who embodies various ingenious maker, fixer and grower skills and knowledge, which are needed in times of transformation and regeneration and/or dystopian apocalypse and collapse (see also Doctorow, 2008; Steffen, 2016 [2008], Kohtala, 2017; Nguyen, 2018). Maker-heroes however are not individuals acting alone, nor would they be able to in the context of our current various environmental and social crises, from widespread economic precarity to biodiversity loss, rampant financialization to global heating, widening rich-poor income gaps to the sixth mass extinction. Solarpunk as a cultural phenomenon or meme does not appear to react to such crises with fear, terror, anger or pessimism, however; it is often associated with ‘hopepunk’ and a non-naïve optimism based on pragmatism, getting one’s hands dirty together with others, and literally building a better world. The maker heroes in such a scenario are thus eco-communities and hacker/makerspaces skilled in eco-tech, Appropriate Technology, circular design and repurposing, and the like.

Nevertheless solarpunk as a young concept largely remains a visual and literary one, explored particularly in science fiction, poetry, art and illustration, animations and game design. Tangible material cultures of design and architecture are depicted, and reference examples from the real world inform the solarpunk narrative, particularly greenery-adorned Bosco Verticale in Milan and a well-known park in Singapore called Gardens by the Bay (see e.g. Heath, 2024). It appears fruitful, then, to examine maker culture from within to see if 'solarpunk' is explicitly inspiring projects or directions in fab labs and – from the other direction – to see if or how those who contribute to a solarpunk imaginary, from its literature traditions, point to or are involved in Actually Existing solarpunk in the wild beyond literary or illustration expressions.

This exploratory study thereby aimed to see links and divergences between and betwixt what has been labelled as solarpunk: if any actual solarpunk material implementations exist beyond the known depictions in architecture; if fab lab and maker projects explicitly align to 'solarpunk'; and finally to examine ecologically oriented fab lab visions and their material implementations to see if or how they may be solarpunk-in-the-wild. My objective has been to use solarpunk as a lens to re-examine fab lab and maker culture today, after it has been institutionalizing over the last twenty years. Such a task may identify emerging pathways and potentials towards sustainability transitions where maker culture plays, I argue, an increasingly relevant role in post-Fordist, ecologically literate, just transitions. The following sections will review the contextual, theoretical and methodological background of the study before turning to the main findings.

2 Socialtechnical imaginaries and utopian visions

Science and Technology Studies (STS) scholars refer to sociotechnical imaginaries as genres or motifs that generate discussion in society, new ideas and new material culture. Imaginaries are visions, narratives and discourses that mobilize actors, inspiring and aligning them in developing technologies and embedding them into social routines and people's everyday lives. For example, Patrice Flichy (2007) examined the role of sociotechnical imaginaries in shaping the internet: how narratives, visions, actors' lobbying, as well as technical development contributed to the development of the internet and World Wide Web from the "information superhighway". A sociotechnical imaginary is thereby often examined (and defined) by scholars in terms of how such visions are shaped at larger national or regional levels: how a society shares an understanding of what it aspires for science and technology (Jasanoff and Kim, 2015). Other scholars nevertheless study how imaginaries as shared visions guide action at smaller scales such as among design teams working on health related technologies (Gregory, 2000; Hyysalo, 2010) or the imaginaries about decentralized autonomous systems at play among blockchain communities (Lustig, 2019). What is important to note is that an *imaginary* is a collectively held vision (Jasanoff, 2015), with "material and political influence to shape the present" (Kanarp, 2024, 3).

Jesse Adams Stein, for instance, has examined the domestication of additive manufacturing equipment into desktop 3D printers in fab labs as "political imaginaries" of 3D printing (Stein, 2017), and Susan Curie Sivek has examined techno-utopian imaginaries via the commodification of maker material culture by corporate interests in mass media publishing (Sivek, 2011). Stein (2017) identified imaginaries around 3D printing as *maker-as-entrepreneur*; the *economic revival of the nation state*; and *commons-based utopias*, visions of the future that serve to excite public imagination, but also mobilize design and designers into pursuits and pathways, making choices about livelihood, project, community and values as they invest their time and skills into particular projects.

In STS scholarship on sociotechnical imaginaries, often the attention is on the interactions of powerful institutional actors such as municipal, regional or national authorities, corporations or universities (e.g. Flichy, 2007; Jasanoff and Kim, 2015), where, as stated, the vision is collectively shared, "materially embedded, and politically dominant" (Kanarp, 2024, 2). Yet when we examine how people play a role in shaping technologies, as well as how technologies shape us (cf. Williams and Edge, 1996), we also see how bottom-up, grassroots social groupings also participate in shaping imaginaries, producing

alternative designs, innovations, products, technologies and the storytelling around them that have effects on dominant imaginaries (Kohtala, Hyysalo and Whalen, 2020; Lechowicz and Kuchler, 2024). The dynamics around actors wielding influence to shape narratives and imaginaries around ‘the New Industrial Revolution’ are visible in fab labs and maker culture particularly in the books on maker culture and sub-themes that are highlighted in large events such as Maker Faires and the International Fab Lab meetings.¹

David J. Hess (2016) also points to the role of groups contesting mainstream technologies and products (e.g. eco-houses, organic food, alternative medicine, or renewable energy technologies) as “industrial transitions movements”. Drawing together analytical concepts from social movement studies, transitions studies and STS, Hess draws attention to the dynamics in “design conflicts”, where groups promote alternative material cultures as challengers to a dominant, incumbent, institutionalized material culture in a society (e.g. groups promoting renewable energy technologies in the face of mainstream, established fossil-fuel-based infrastructures). Such design conflicts are more than just material artefacts: symbols and discourses (such as “information superhighway”) become means by which social groupings negotiate and express their ambitions, as “institutional logics” (Friedland and Alford, 1991).

Yet maker culture is itself not the dominant imaginary related to production and manufacturing; it is a challenger offering several visions of the future, as Stein (2017), Braybrooke and Jordan (2017), and others have highlighted. That is, within maker culture imaginaries arise other alternatives as challengers, such as feminist hacking (e.g. Toupin, 2014), maker coops (Smith, 2020), or low-tech labs (Meyer, 2022), in what could be seen as technological dramas (Pfaffenberger, 1992). Is solarpunk such an emerging imaginary in fab labs?

3 Methods

The research approach for this paper was that of an exploratory scoping study examining current and emerging eco-fab lab and solarpunk aesthetics, material culture and design culture, and subculture (or counter-culture) discourse and visions in online sources. To understand the key characteristics of solarpunk, its history and how solarpunk is being referenced and represented, I examined academic literature as well as online grey literature sources referencing solarpunk. I briefly reviewed Fab Academy final projects (2012-2023) to gain familiarity with the range of projects that have been conducted and how the fablabbers described and positioned them.² I also searched for other maker and fab lab projects documented online that either explicitly aligned with solarpunk by name or invoked solarpunk, eco-futurism, energy awareness or ecological consciousness in other ways. I did not aim to cast a wide net to systematically capture ‘everything’ in terms of grey literature texts or projects, but rather reviewed key blogs, the solarpunk sub-Reddit, posts in the social network Mastodon, and using snowball source searching to identify writings and projects to gain an overall image, potentially the initial corpus on how a ‘solarpunk’ imaginary is now being collectively formed.³ I then clustered the materials in terms of

¹ For a useful summary of the imaginary of the new industrial revolution and maker ideology, see Hepp and Schmitz (2022).

² I examined mainly the main presentation slide (title and description) and checked the project description further in some cases. A more systematic examination and analysis could be conducted in future, but this was not the aim in this study.

³ I recognize the limits of such a search where search results are biased according to my previous search strings. However, for this exploratory study, I believe I identified key texts on solarpunk that are often cited by others and the main academic papers in an adequate manner. Projects including Fab Academy projects were collected according to mentions of environmental impacts, climate change, energy consumption and renewable energy, but also any Fab Academy project concerning agriculture and plants, nature, the environment, and similar were examined in order to identify characteristics that could be compared to those ascribed most often to solarpunk in online discourse.

artefact and function, relation to environmental issues, visual aesthetics, and in vivo sociomaterial qualities, such as the stated reason for developing the project and for what or whom it is aimed. Concepts on sociotechnical imaginaries, social worlds, utopias, and industrial transitions movements from STS scholarship guided the analysis and the positioning of this study (Hess, 2005; Clarke and Star, 2008; Levitas, 2013).

4 Solarpunk, and where to find it

Solarpunk as a term first emerged in a blog post in 2008 (Republic of the Bees, 2008), in Brazilian science fiction in 2012, and its aesthetics explored in e.g. a viral Tumblr post by user Olivia Louise in 2015 (see Springett, 2017; Wilk, 2018). Besides Tumblrs, subReddits, Instagram hashtags, anthologies, and print and online magazines, solarpunk continues to evolve online as “moodboard” collections of discussions and images (Williams, 2019, 7). Visual aesthetics of solarpunk cities and architecture, usually in artistic representations, are often compared to those of Studio Ghibli’s animations, to garden cities and organic forms, and Art Nouveau and the Arts and Crafts movement in design history. Importantly it is also acknowledged that discourses and aesthetics – and indeed their politics – vary for solarpunk as an emerging concept (Hudson, 2015; Wilk, 2018). Solarpunk is seen to either emerge after collapse or in the midst of it – as a way to stave off apocalypse, and hence qualities related to DIY, reuse and resilience as capacities needed for sustainability transitions also come bundled with the solarpunk genre – as “post-industrial design”, as Eric Hunting compellingly calls it (2020).

The bulk of academic literature referencing solarpunk does remain in the literary realm (literature studies) analysing science fiction and environmental discourses. More recently solarpunk also appears in papers from other fields such as geography and social sciences, where it serves researchers in naming imaginaries, i.e. existing community discourses on renewable energy or urban infrastructures, or as a symbolic motif offering alternative eco-narratives for co-imagining alternative futures. A number of articles reference using solarpunk within futuring methods, such as using solarpunk concepts when co-designing desirable futures through storytelling with rural communities in Colombia (Reina-Rozo et al., 2024). Such a theme occurs also in education studies where solarpunk is invoked when working with students with themes of optimism and hope and to foster new types of sustainability competences deemed necessarily in today’s complex world (e.g. Nørgård and Holflod, 2024). Solarpunk is at times an implicit concept invoked by authors in projects that put scientists together with artists and designers on climate change issues – mentioned as having aesthetic resonance (Tosca et al., 2021) – and explicit in other projects where artists work with citizens on environmental issues important in their peripheral geographical locality, e.g. the Rjukan Solarpunk Academy in Norway (Coenen, 2023). As in online discourse, solarpunk representations in the academic literature are at times described as even being technocentric and at others aligned with postcolonial imagination and postgrowth futures.

The emphasis on storytelling and either narrative, literary forms or visual illustration, particularly in online discourse, lends the impression that ‘solarpunk’ is a genre that is rarely actually practiced or used as a motif in eco-social making and prototyping, apart from community-engaged art projects. Compared to steampunk, which boasts an active community of makers and hobbyists, and events devoted to it, solarpunk has only very recently been used as a motif for climate events and small design conferences (e.g. Coenen, 2023).⁴ Moreover, an examination of human-computer interaction literature (the ACM Digital Library), where documentation and conceptualization of interactive prototypes constitute a significant proportion of studies, reveals surprisingly few actual projects aligning explicitly with solarpunk and studies referencing solarpunk rather discussing urban imaginaries. Given the promise of solarpunk to draw together collectives of maker-heroes with repair and bricolage skills, not to mention skills to produce food, energy, and low-environmental-footprint housing and transportation, this is somewhat surprising. That eco-social and eco-futurist maker communities – and their projects and prototypes – do indeed exist is not the question, nor do they need to align with solarpunk imagery to accomplish their

⁴ Steampunk is also often noted in critiques as a commodified and consumerist maker subculture.

work. Yet solarpunk's speculative vision-making have material implications, and researchers have suggested that the material dimension of imaginaries have power to mobilize, especially in ecological discourses: how imaginaries "influence concrete practices of inhabiting the Earth" (Roux-Rosier et al., 2018, 551).

Is such a dynamic then traceable in fab lab and maker culture? In a pragmatic way, ecologically oriented maker projects, spaces and events have influenced others and had knock-on effects years later, such as the networks of actors built after POC21, the circularity-oriented maker camp in France in 2015 (Conrad, 2016). Open Source Ecology has been much referenced and Global Village Construction Sets prototyped globally (e.g. Quilley et al., 2016; see also Eakin, 2013). Visits to, for example, Valldaura Self-Sufficiency Lab in Barcelona and Vigyan Ashram FabLab in India inspire others in orienting to ecologically focused work, and projects within labs and documented in Fab Academy archives are referenced by other fablabbers.⁵ A fab lab in Oregon is even called Solarpunk SEED, explicitly describing it as a place to actualize the "solarpunk commons".⁶

In my overview of Fab Academy project presentation posters, I did not come across solarpunk as an explicit descriptor. There were nevertheless projects oriented explicitly to 'solar' in the descriptors or even in the project name, such as solar trackers and even tools for solar PV panels such as robot cleaners. Projects that mentioned 'low tech' and energy saving tools had, as I saw them, solarpunk type characteristics, as were those that explicitly aimed to use existing resources, reused components and materials found locally. Several projects mentioned wishing for enhanced relationships to nature and/or the environment, and these were often artistic oriented speculative installations or devices. Many projects by architects and architecture students noted interest in responsive façades reacting to the sun; most descriptions emphasized stronger interest in geometries and automation and thus came across rather technocentric, while some expressed a motivation connected to environmental reasons, global heating and climate change adaptation, experimenting with vernacular building techniques combined with fab lab capabilities, and other qualities more akin, I would argue, to a solarpunk orientation. A similar tendency could be noted with the many projects concerned with growing plants and small-scale agriculture. Hydroponics and aquaponics projects featured notably, as did various solutions for sensing plant health and hydration levels. Again, the descriptors most often noted the motivation as simply keeping houseplants healthy or an interest in growing edible plants indoors, while several projects explicitly mentioned wider environmental concern with food security, self-sufficiency, and land use in urban and rural areas. Such projects tied themselves to broader awareness of resource availability and environmentalism, compared to simply having one's houseplants watered, as well as digital and technological autonomy. In sum, it appears increasingly many Fab Academy final projects aim to tangibly realize solarpunk ambitions even without being named as such.

5 Solarpunk, and how to do it

Examining the narratives and practices around solarpunk as it is being explored today, and relating them to maker culture narratives as well as realized projects and practices, sheds light on environmentally oriented pathways in current and emerging maker cultures. Solarpunk is associated with art-based speculative future storytelling as well as community-based interventions; low-energy, yet not necessarily small-scale, transportation, housing and food production; urban planning based on more-than-human design principles; a renewed focus on resource flows in bio-regions; and similar directions to mobilize makers into action. Moreover, when used as a lens on maker culture, solarpunk shines a spotlight on fab

⁵ Indeed, Fab Academy students are asked to identify projects done previously that are similar to the one they wish to pursue.

⁶ <https://www.solarpunkseed.net>

lab imaginaries that have shaped the movement as it has evolved and in some ways institutionalized, including ways it has acknowledged and ignored principles of environmental justice.

For one, in recent years there have been regular critiques of the dominant images and discourses of the maker movement, critical views that see maker culture globally represented merely as tech-tinkering for young, elite white men in restricted, exclusive spaces. This view suggests that global maker culture actively invisibilizes other types of spaces and places and presents hagiographies of Silicon Valley individual heroes as the official histories of making (Sivek, 2011; Braybrooke and Jordan, 2017; Lindtner and Lin, 2017; Kohtala, Boeva and Troxler, 2020). Acknowledging such gaps aims to hold space for other practices, geographies, spaces and histories of making. Other types of ecologically oriented labs have indeed recently become more prominent, from eco-design and circular fab labs to maker coops oriented to alternative economic organizing and postgrowth principles (Smith, 2020). Yet particularly the latter is associated with new forms of governance and indicators of success that eschew classical economics models (Gibson-Graham, 2008). Despite writers espousing solarpunk as clearly a degrowth imaginary, these alternative ways to self-organize appear to be visible mainly only in the science fiction novels that bear the solarpunk genre. Nor do I perceive that fab lab imaginaries of the new industrial revolution offer a route to these alternative ways to organize and self-govern beyond notions of 'p2p organizing' after the tradition of free open source software development, despite two decades of 'experimenting' with organizing.

In addition, solarpunk imaginaries remind us that early writers about fab lab culture tended to offer the narrative that fab labs were the descendants of the radical design and technology movements that emerged during the energy crisis of the 1970s and carried on their principles (Mandavilli, 2006; Pearce, 2012; Smith et al., 2017), particularly those of Appropriate Technology (Schumacher, 1973) and Alternative Technology (Boyle and Harper, 1976). The early fab labs being established in the global South, communicated as mainly serving low-income regions and "developing countries", were espoused as fruitful territory for appropriate technology development. This conception belies the history and intent of the alternative technology movement which aimed to motivate small environmental footprints and diffuse small-is-beautiful tech in the resource guzzling global North (e.g. Harper and Sadler, 2020). A solarpunk maker ethos as espoused by writers such as Flynn (2014), Hudson (2015) and Hunting (2020) certainly promotes this: solarpunk in this conceptualization is a cosmological guiding imaginary where the principles of *jugaad*, *gambiarra*, and so on, can (and should) also transform design, technology, manufacturing and production in the global North and wealthy regions. Appropriate technology in such an imaginary is thereby seen, not as a 'development tool' to bridge digital divides in the global South, but rather as a levelling device that can recalibrate neoliberal, modernist and capitalist conceptions of technology and innovation. How environmental justice can be understood, embraced and enacted thereby appears to be uneven and fragmented in both solarpunk and fab lab imaginaries.

The following table lists key qualities of fab lab and solarpunk imaginaries, with the third column indicating some of these slippages and gaps mentioned above. Such qualities are often written about as being embraced by solarpunk, yet they remain rather in the form of utopian narrative vision in sci-fi stories than Actually Existing community experiments: as the anti-dystopian prefigurative material politics of building the new in the ruins of the old (cf. Wright, 2013).

Table 1: Qualities of fab lab and solarpunk imaginaries

	FabLabs and the New Industrial Revolution	Solarpunk	An emerging middle ground?
Focus	free, open source digital fabrication tools and software	renewable energy, solar, low energy, nature consciousness	principles of diverse economies ⁷ in hyperlocal, ecologically oriented making
	human-tech-human relations	human-nature-tech relations	nature-tech relations embedding human/social
	new form/mode of prosumer production (compared to mass production/ consumption)	ecotopia, eco-futurism (compared to environmental collapse and dystopia)	community in webs of life making appropriately (compared to large scale ecomodernist geoengineering)
Action	autonomous and local development of tech according to need (individual and community), also novel and hedonistic needs	autonomous, DIY development of tech according to basic collective human needs (e.g. food, housing)	autonomous and community development of innovative forms of governance, to foster locally relevant, place-based making and being
Visual aesthetics	proof-of-concept, microcontrollers, silicon	organic, garden-centric, solar	organo-cybernetic, rhizomatic, bricolage
Organizing	action-based foo, p2p as adopted from FLOSS development practices, centred on material prototypes and documentation	literary and visual discourse centred on being inspiring, mobilizing activism; material, collective experimentation as emerging form	action-based, cross-disciplinary, community process in networked cooperatives based on value flows ⁸
Co-optation	autonomy yet usually aligned with current capitalism and mainstream	ideology represented in visual aesthetics and discourse easily coopted by business-as-usual and current	commons-based governance models and knowledge practices that challenge co-optation

⁷ Gibson-Graham, 2008

⁸ Mikorizal, n.d.

		capitalism	
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6 Conclusions

This paper has examined qualities of solarpunk as an ecologically oriented sociotechnical imaginary that wields influence from the literary realm and is impacting discourse and even practices in art, design and architecture. The aim of the study is not to attempt yet another definition of solarpunk, but rather to map its discourse and qualities in relation to ecological oriented maker culture. The paper also aimed to explore the dynamics around the social shaping of sociotechnical imaginaries and how or if societal wide imaginaries can be influenced from below. Emerging STS literature on sociotechnical imaginaries, social movements and counter-cultures acknowledges the role of bottom-up social groupings in shaping discourses even while influences are challenging to directly identify and the dynamics play out over long time periods.

Solarpunk is little explicitly represented thus far in fab lab discourse or practice, yet there are signs that it has potential to inspire makers into environmentally oriented, low-energy and renewable-energy-powered experiments, perhaps in a more focused and compelling way than other concepts such as ‘eco-design’ or ‘circular design’ can. Solarpunk is also described by writers as showing new ways to organize and self-govern in postgrowth oriented communities making things and being together convivially and softly on Earth. Nevertheless there is as yet little evidence of this trajectory being taken in the fab lab sociotechnical imaginary, and orientations in maker culture to eco-feminist, postcolonial, postgrowth perspectives on environmental justice are fragmented.

The principle of solarpunk, which is something like, “if this is apocalypse then we should mobilize”, shows us that there are tensions in maker promises when it comes to mobilization, as indicated by the response to the pandemic notwithstanding some successes (Hepp and Schmitz, 2022). Maker culture generally currently operates distinctly from activist movements such as 15-M and Occupy, who not only protested, but also built new organizing structures as prefigurative politics. Those who can do stuff in fab labs, makerspaces and hackerspaces are not always the folks oriented to – or amenable to – alternative organizing, experimenting with alternative economies, or setting up coops, even if such structures could provide more resilient livelihoods, equity, and resistance to co-optation. Perhaps solarpunk as a mobilizing imaginary could provide some footholds here with its very materialist pragmatism in the face of dystopian environmental and social collapse. As researcher G.C.S. was told by pessimistic interviewees facing the very real and visible effects of climate change in the Arctic, the growth paradigm was likely the source of the problem but they did not see a way out of it. Society will end and “your research or my tinkering with projects here in the far north won’t change anything” (Kanarp, 2024, 11). Yet it would be the tinkering with projects that could provide, if not a utopia, then at least an anti-dystopia, as Kim Stanley Robinson would call it. Solarpunk tinkering is, if anything, both locally present and forward looking.

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